

Hypertension, endothelial tyrosine hydroxylase, and hypoxia

Johan Nygren, johanngrn@gmail.com

Endothelium expresses tyrosine hydroxylase (TH), and tyrosine hydroxylase gene expression increases with hypoxia (Sorriento, 2012). This is likely part of endocrine regulation of the heart by organs such as skeletal muscle.

High blood pressure compresses the vasa vasorum, and causes hypoxia in the vessel wall (Sacks, 1975).

Chronic high blood pressure leads to chronic hypoxia in the vessel wall, and necrosis.

Cholesterol is always present during wound healing. Correlates with macrophage presence (Bagnati, 2019).

A hypothetical disturbed feedback loop during chronic hypertension is that endothelium interprets signals during vessel wall ischemia, infarction and inflammation caused by hypertension compressing vasa vasorum as a cue for failed blood perfusion, and responds reflexively by activating the endothelium-adrenaline-heart axis to order the heart to supply blood. The activation of this axis worsens the hypertension, in turn upregulating the endothelium-adrenaline-heart axis reflex even more.

References

Sorriento, D., Santulli, G., Del Giudice, C., Anastasio, A., Trimarco, B., & Iaccarino, G. (2012). Endothelial Cells Are Able to Synthesize and Release Catecholamines Both In Vitro and In Vivo. *Hypertension*, 60(1), 129–136.

<https://doi.org/10.1161/hypertensionaha.111.189605>

Sacks, A. H. (1975). The Vasa Vasorum as a Link Between Hypertension and Arteriosclerosis. *Angiology*, 26(5), 385–390.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/000331977502600503>

Bagnati, M., Moreno-Moral, A., Ko, J.-H., Nicod, J., Harmston, N., Imprialou, M., Game, L., Gil, J., Petretto, E., & Behmoaras, J. (2019). Systems genetics identifies a macrophage cholesterol network associated with physiological wound healing. *JCI Insight*, 4(2). <https://doi.org/10.1172/jci.insight.125736>